

Installing QGIS 3.10

QGIS is an open source software for working with GIS data. The tool is constantly updated with new versions, for this training, we will be using the 3.10 version of the tool. Follow the below steps to download and install the program. **It is very important that you install 3.10 for the training, since otherwise the tutorials will not work correctly.**

1. Download the installation executable by clicking on the following link:
https://qgis.org/downloads/QGIS-OSGeo4W-3.10.7-1-Setup-x86_64.exe
2. Double-click on the executable once it has been downloaded to your personal computer.
3. The first window will be a welcoming window, click "Next"

4. The second window will include all the licenses that you have to agree with in order to get QGIS installed. Click on "I agree"

5. Next, you will be prompted to select install location. This is where your QGIS version will be installed. It is recommended to go with the default on i.e. **C:\Program Files\QGIS 3.10** (or similar). When the installation path is determined click on "Next".

6. In the last step you will be asked to choose components. This includes QGIS itself but also a number of different test datasets. In this workshop we will not be using any test datasets, so you can leave these boxes unchecked (see image below). When finished click “Install”

7. When the installation is finished click on **Finish**. Test to start QGIS (called **QGIS Desktop 3.10.7 with GRASS** on your computer).